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Bt rice: practical steps to sustainable use

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Introduction

In 1996, maize, cotton, and potato farmers in the USA became the first farmers in the world to grow transgenic insect-resistant cultivars. These cultivars contain genes from the bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*) that encode insecticidal proteins known as delta-endotoxins. Delta-endotoxins have two properties that are essential for toxins used in transgenic crops: they are highly toxic to certain insect pests, and they are generally safe for human consumption (NRC 2000). *Bt* crops have been a large commercial success. In 1999, 11.7 million ha of *Bt* crops were grown by farmers in 10 countries, including Australia, Canada, China, South Africa, Spain, and the USA (James 1999).

Many laboratories around the world have transformed rice with *Bt* genes and have evaluated their effectiveness under greenhouse conditions (e.g., Cheng et al 1998, Datta et al 1998, Maqbool et al 1998). No *Bt* rice varieties have yet been released to farmers, but field testing began at two sites in China in 1998 (Datta 1999, Ye et al 2000). The target pests for control by *Bt* rice are caterpillars, most importantly the yellow stem borer (YSB, *Scirpophaga incertulas*), the striped stem borer (SSB, *Chilo suppressalis*), and leafrollers such as *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. It has not been possible to produce rice with high resistance to these pests through conventional breeding, although short-duration semidwarf varieties are generally less damaged by stem borers than are traditional varieties (Khan et al 1991).

Genetic engineering with *Bt* genes is a powerful technology for protecting crops against some kinds of insects. *Bt* cultivars, however, have the same weakness as many other insect control technologies: insects can evolve resistance to them, thereby eliminating their effectiveness.¹ Insects have evolved resistance to all classes of widely used insecticides, including *Bt* products that are applied as sprays (Frutos et al 1999). Insects have also adapted to numerous resistant crop varieties produced through conventional breeding. Notable examples in rice include the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens* (Heinrichs 1986), and the Asian rice gall midge, *Orseolia oryzae* (Bennett et al 2000).

The problem of insect adaptation to insecticides and resistant cultivars results in substantial costs to society, as crop failures, environmental damage, and loss of useful products. This has stimulated extensive research on the genetic and biochemical basis of resistance, and the development of “resistance management” strategies that can extend the effectiveness of insecticides and cultivars. In this review, we describe some practical steps that can be taken to delay the evolution of pest resistance to *Bt* rice.

The “high-dose/refuge” resistance management strategy

Over the past 10 years, scientists, government regulators, environmentalists, and the private sector have vigorously debated if and how the evolution of pest resistance to *Bt* crops can be delayed (e.g., Mellon and Rissler 1998, Gould 1998). There is widespread agreement that one strategy—the “high-dose/refuge” strategy—is the most promising and practical approach to prolonging the effectiveness of *Bt* crops. The high-dose/refuge strategy is being enforced for *Bt* cotton, maize, and potato in the USA (EPA-USDA 1999), *Bt* maize in Canada (CFIA 1999), and *Bt* cotton in Australia (ACGRA-TIMS 1997).

To understand how the high-dose/refuge strategy works, it is necessary to examine the genetic basis of resistance. In many cases, resistance to an insecticide is caused by a mutation in one gene of an insect. If there are two possible forms of the gene (alleles), i.e., R (the mutant allele, conferring resistance) and S (the normal allele, conferring susceptibility), and each insect has two copies of the gene, then there are three possible genetic types (genotypes) of insects: SS, RS, and RR. Figure 1 illustrates the response of each genotype to increasing concentrations of an insecticide. In this example, the response of RS insects to the insecticide is intermediate between that of the SS and RR insects, but is more similar to that of the SS insects, indicating that the R allele is partially recessive [as it is in many cases of resistance to *Bt* toxins (Frutos et al 1999)]. To implement the high-dose/refuge strategy, it is necessary to have a titer of toxin in the *Bt* cultivar

that is high enough to kill almost all of the RS insects (indicated by the dotted line in Figure 1).

“Refuges” are non-*Bt* crop plants that serve to maintain *Bt*-susceptible insects in the population. Refuges can consist of fields planted with non-*Bt* plants or of non-*Bt* plants within fields of *Bt* plants. The large number of insects with the SS genotype that survive on the refuge plants are then available to mate with the small number of RS insects that survive on the *Bt* plants (Fig. 2). The offspring of SS × RR matings will be RS, and therefore will not survive when they feed on high-dose *Bt* plants.

It might seem that a high dose of toxin in *Bt* cultivars would accelerate the evolution of pest resistance rather than delay it. The output of a simple population genetics model, however, shows that if refuges are maintained, high-dose plants are more durable than low-dose plants (Fig. 3).

Which spatial arrangement of refuge plants is best depends on the biology of the pest. Mixtures of *Bt* and non-*Bt* plants within fields can be established by sowing seed mixtures or by planting rows of refuge plants within fields of *Bt* plants. Within-field mixtures are not the best type of refuge for insects that move between plants during development. This is because some of the insects will feed on *Bt* and non-*Bt* plants, thereby “diluting” the high-dose titer in *Bt* plants (Gould 1998). Most larvae of YSB and SSB move between plants during development (Cohen et al 2000).

If separate refuge fields are established, then *Bt* fields must not be too far from a refuge field, or else there might not be random mating between the RR and SS insect genotypes. Therefore, it is important to know approximately how far the adult pest insects will move before mating. This question is being studied at IRRI for YSB and SSB (A.M. Dirie, N.L. Cuong, F. Gould, and M.B. Cohen, unpubl.). Based on our current knowledge of YSB and SSB biology, it appears that maintaining separate refuge fields within 1 km of *Bt* rice fields would be a suitable form of refuge.

Fig. 1. Dose-response lines indicating the mortality of three insect genotypes at increasing concentrations of an insecticidal toxin. The dotted line indicates the concentration required for a “high dose.” S, allele conferring susceptibility; R, allele conferring resistance.

¹Note that the word “resistance” is used in two ways, which can sometimes be confusing. Cultivars can be produced that have “resistance” to insects; and insects can evolve “resistance” to insecticides, such as *Bt* toxins in transgenic plants.

Fig. 2. How the high-dose/refuge strategy works to delay the increase in highly resistant (RR) insects in a pest population.

Fig. 3. Rate of evolution of pest resistance to *Bt* plants under various conditions, as simulated by a population genetics model. Settings of model parameters are as follows: Both low-dose (panel A) and high-dose (panel B) plants kill 100% of the SS insects and 0% of the RR insects. On low-dose plants, 5% of the RS insects survive to maturity; while on high-dose plants, only 0.5% of the RS insects survive. The initial frequency of the R allele is 10^{-3} .

The model output indicates that if the low-dose cultivar is grown in 90% of the crop fields and the remaining fields serve as a non-*Bt* refuge, resistance to the *Bt* toxin evolves in about 15 pest generations. Under the same conditions, the high-dose cultivar remains effective for about 45 pest generations. If no refuge is maintained, resistance evolves in less than five generations on both cultivars. In tropical irrigated areas, there are approximately six generations of rice stem borers per year.

How can "high-dose" plants be identified?

When plants are transformed, transgenes become incorporated into plant chromosomes at random locations. For this and other reasons, there is great variability among independent transgenic lines in the level of transgene expression. Because toxin titers

can differ substantially among plant lines that are transformed with the same *Bt* gene construct (e.g., Cheng et al 1998, Datta et al 1998, Maqbool et al 1998), many transformed lines must be screened to identify a few that produce adequate quantities of *Bt* toxin and do not have agronomic problems such as stunted growth.

Dose-response data. Plants have a “high dose” of toxin when they are able to kill almost all insects of the RS genotype (Fig. 1). To make practical use of this definition, a resistant colony of the pest must be available so that RS insects can be tested. Unfortunately, *Bt*-resistant colonies of YSB or SSB have not been developed. A high dose has also been defined as one that is 25X higher than that required to kill 99% of homozygous susceptible insects (EPA 1998). To make practical use of this definition, it is necessary to have an accurate estimate of the LD₉₉, determined from dose-response experiments using purified *Bt* toxin. No rigorous estimates of the LD₉₉ for *Bt* toxins against YSB or SSB have been published. We have not been able to obtain reliable estimates of LD₅₀ or LD₉₉ values at IRRI due to very high variability between experiments (R. Aguda, F. Gould, and M.B. Cohen, unpubl.).

Plant bioassays. Another way to determine if a *Bt* rice line has a high dose of toxin is to test it against a large number of stem borer larvae and verify that very few insects survive to maturity. A large number of test larvae is necessary because RR insects are likely to be rare. A study of the tobacco budworm in the USA found that the frequency of an allele conferring high resistance to Cry1Ab and other *Bt* toxins was 1.5×10^{-3} (Gould et al 1997). A population of YSB in the Philippines was found to have a frequency of alleles conferring high resistance to Cry1Ab of less than 3.6×10^{-3} , with 95% confidence (Bentur et al 2000). If the frequency of an allele for *Bt* resistance in a pest population is 10^{-3} (meaning that 1 out of 1,000 copies of the resistance gene has the R allele), then the frequency of RR insects of the population would be 10^{-6} . If such a population were in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium, then the frequency of RS insects would be approximately 2×10^{-3} and that of SS insects would be about 0.998. On a high-dose *Bt* cultivar that killed all of the SS insects, 99.5% of the RS insects, and none of the RR insects, only about 10 out of 1 million insects would survive to maturity!

Typically, greenhouse evaluations of *Bt* rice lines use only a few dozen or perhaps a few hundred larvae. With these small numbers of test insects, even plants with a very low dose of toxin will probably kill 100% of test insects, almost all of which will be of the SS genotype. **Thus, 100% larval mortality in a typical greenhouse bioassay does not indicate that the *Bt* line has a high dose of toxin, as defined in terms of the high-dose/refuge strategy.**

What about field evaluations of *Bt* rice plants? Imagine a 100-m² test plot of *Bt* rice, transplanted at 20 × 20 cm spacing, and one seedling per hill. Such a field would contain 2,500 plants. If every plant were artificially infested with one stem borer egg mass at vegetative stage, and a second egg mass at booting stage, and each egg mass contained 100 eggs, and there were no natural infestation, then there would be 500,000 larvae in the plot during the growing season. If the plant killed all of the SS insects, 99.5% of the RS insects, and none of the RR insects, and there were no mortality caused by natural enemies or other non-*Bt* factors, then about 5 insects would survive to maturity. This would result in about 10 deadhearts or whiteheads in the entire plot. If there were 10 panicles per plant, this would be equivalent to a damage level of about 0.04% whiteheads. Calculations such as these should be made when researchers evaluate the performance of *Bt* rice in field tests.

Quantification of toxin titer. Comparisons with commercially released *Bt* cotton, maize, and potato cultivars can provide guidance on what is a high-toxin titer dose in *Bt* rice. Three released cultivars in the USA are considered to have a high dose of toxin against all target pests, based on extensive experimental evaluation and experience in farmers’ fields (see table). The toxin titer in these cultivars ranges from 1 to 11 μg g⁻¹ of leaf fresh weight or 0.1% to 0.2% of soluble leaf protein.

A *Bt* toxin titer of 0.2% of soluble leaf protein is well within reach of what can be achieved with rice (e.g., Cheng et al 1998,

Characteristics of commercially available *Bt* cultivars.

Crop	Transformation event (company)	<i>Bt</i> toxin	Approximate maximum toxin titer		Principal target pests	Does the event have a high dose? ^a
			μg g ⁻¹ leaf fresh weight ^b	% soluble leaf protein		
Potato	na ^c (Monsanto)	Cry3A	na	0.1–0.2 ^d	Colorado potato beetle	Yes
Cotton	Events 531 and 931 (Monsanto)	CryIAc	1–2	na	Cotton bollworm	No
					Tobacco budworm	Yes
					Pink bollworm	Yes
Maize	Event Bt11 (Novartis)	CryIAb	3	na	European corn borer	Yes
Maize	Event MON810 (Monsanto)	CryIAb	5–11	na	European corn borer	Yes
Maize	Event 176 (Novartis, Mycogen)	CryIAb	4	0.2 ^e	European corn borer	Vegetative stage: yes Reproductive stage: no

^aGould 1998, Mellon and Rissler 1998. ^bUS Environmental Protection Agency fact sheets (<http://www.epa.gov/pesticides/biopesticides/>). ^cna = not available. ^dFeldman and Stone 1997. ^eKoziel et al 1993.

Datta et al 1998, Maqbool et al 1998). This toxin titer could be considered as a guideline for the minimum titer for high-dose *Bt* rice plants. For successful resistance management, it must also be demonstrated that the high-toxin titer is maintained over the entire period of pest attack. Toxin titer declines substantially at reproductive stage in a maize line (Mellon and Rissler 1998) and a rice line (Alinia et al 2000) with a cry1Ab gene under control of the PEP C promoter. Toxin decline at later stages of plant growth has also been observed under some environmental conditions for *Bt* cotton with the CaMV 35S promoter (Fitt et al 1998).

How can refuges be maintained?

Farmers growing *Bt* crops in the USA must plant 4–20% of their land to non-*Bt* cultivars, and these refuge fields must be within approximately 0.8 km of their *Bt* fields (EPA-USDA 1999). Obviously, enforcing a similar system for small rice farmers will not be possible in most parts of Asia. This does not mean, however, that a functional high-dose/refuge strategy cannot be achieved for *Bt* rice. In a typical village, it is unlikely that all farmers will plant *Bt* rice on all their land. *Bt* genes will be one of many factors that farmers will consider when choosing which rice varieties to grow. Governments can promote the maintenance of refuges by restricting the number and diversity of *Bt* cultivars that can be released. For example, in the Indian state of Punjab, farmers grow traditional Basmati varieties and modern semidwarf varieties. Stem borer damage is higher in Basmati varieties, and thus the government could authorize the release of *Bt*-transformed Basmati varieties but not *Bt*-transformed semidwarfs.

Because of the great importance of maintaining refuges, governments should also consider implementing a refuge system where this would be practical. Examples include large rice-growing estates or collectives, villages with well-organized farmers' organizations, and areas with strong extension services.

The concern is often raised that stem borer damage in non-*Bt* fields will increase after introducing *Bt* rice. The implication is that farmers will be even less likely to grow non-*Bt* rice because of the increased damage, and therefore there will be even fewer refuge fields. In fact, after the introduction of *Bt* rice, the level of stem borer damage in non-*Bt* rice fields will probably be unchanged or will decline. Moths do not prefer to lay their eggs on non-*Bt* plants (Riggin-Bucci and Gould 1997, Hellmich et al 1999), and there is no evidence that moths can detect whether or not a plant contains *Bt* toxin. In some studies, it has been found that, after feeding begins, caterpillars move away from *Bt* plants faster than from non-*Bt* plants (e.g., Dirie et al 2000), but very few rice stem borer larvae crawl far enough to move from one field to another (Cohen et al 2000).

Stem borer moths are good fliers and are well capable of moving from one field to another (Khan et al 1991; A. Dirie, F. Gould, and M.B. Cohen, unpubl.). Many of the moths that emerge from fields of non-*Bt* rice will disperse and lay their eggs in fields of *Bt* rice. In contrast, because very few moths will emerge from

Bt fields, very few moths will move from *Bt* fields to non-*Bt* fields. As a consequence, the amount of stem borer damage in non-*Bt* fields may decline if most fields are planted to *Bt* rice. This decline in damage in refuge fields, called the halo effect, has been observed in experiments with the diamondback moth on *Bt* collards (Riggin-Bucci and Gould 1997) and the European corn borer on *Bt* maize (Andow and Hutchinson 1998).

The importance of two-toxin *Bt* rice

Another practical step that governments can take to promote the sustainable use of *Bt* rice is to release *Bt* cultivars only if they contain two *Bt* toxins, both at a high dose. If insects that are able to survive on a plant with one high-dose toxin are rare, then insects that are able to survive on plants with two high-dose toxins will be very rare indeed. If such insects must be homozygous for resistance alleles for two different genes, and if the frequency of the allele for resistance of each gene is 10^{-3} , then insects of the genotype $R_1R_1R_2R_2$ will occur at a frequency of only 10^{-12} , i.e., 1 out of 1 trillion. Because such insects will be very rare, fewer susceptible insects will be needed to ensure that resistant insects do not mate with each other. Therefore, fewer refuge fields will be necessary (although it is still very important to have some refuge fields).

More than 100 *Bt* toxin genes have been cloned and sequenced; the toxins are highly divergent in amino acid sequence and some biochemical properties (Frutos et al 1999). Any two *Bt* toxins that are used in combination must not be too similar to each other, otherwise, a single mutation could confer "cross-resistance" to both toxins. In most cases that have been studied, insect resistance to *Bt* toxins is caused by mutations in receptor proteins in the insect gut (Frutos et al 1999). Toxins must bind to receptors to initiate the process that will ultimately kill the insect, and mutations in receptors can eliminate toxin binding. Biochemical tests can determine whether two *Bt* toxins bind to the same receptor, and thus whether one mutation might disrupt the effectiveness of both toxins. Based on studies done by Fiuza et al (1996) and Lee et al (1997), it is known that the following are good toxin combinations for both YSB and SSB: Cry1Aa or Cry1Ac with Cry1C or Cry2A. Both studies also found that Cry1Aa and Cry1Ac should not be used in combination. Recently, it has been found that Cry1Ab with Cry1Ac would not be a good combination for either YSB or SSB, but that Cry1Ab with Cry1C or Cry2A would be effective (E. Alcantara, R. Aguda, D. Dean, and M.B. Cohen, unpubl.).

Cotton producing the Cry1Ac and Cry2A toxins has been produced by Monsanto and approved for field testing by the US Environmental Protection Agency (http://www.epa.gov/oppbppd1/biopesticides/reg_activ/reg_act_all_byAI.htm). Maqbool and Christou (1999) transformed rice with genes for the Cry1Ac and Cry2A toxins and found several lines in which the levels of both toxins were >0.5% of soluble leaf protein. Additional laboratories are expected to produce two-toxin *Bt* rice soon.

A computer model of the evolution of *Bt* resistance shows that much of the long-term utility of cultivars with two toxins can be lost if both one- and two-toxin cultivars are grown in the same region, or if one-toxin cultivars are widely grown prior to the release of two-toxin cultivars (F. Gould, J. Van Duyn, and G. Kennedy, unpubl.). Therefore, it is critical to develop appropriate two-toxin cultivars and not to first deploy one-toxin cultivars. An important long-term goal is transformation of plants with combinations of a *Bt* toxin gene and a gene encoding an unrelated toxin because some insect mutations can confer cross-resistance to multiple, distantly related *Bt* toxins (Frutos et al 1999).

Summary and recommendations

Four practical recommendations for promoting the sustainable use of *Bt* rice can be made, based on existing knowledge of the biology of YSB and SSB and the principles of resistance management:

1. Do not release *Bt* varieties that do not have a high dose of toxin. Toxin titers of 2 µg g⁻¹ of leaf fresh weight or 0.2% of soluble leaf protein are attainable in rice, and have been shown to act as high doses against most pests in other crops.
2. Release only *Bt* cultivars that have two *Bt* toxin genes. The genes should not be closely related to each other, and both should be expressed at a high dose. Two-toxin cultivars require smaller refuges to achieve successful resistance management.
3. Do not release *Bt*-transformed versions of all popular rice varieties. Some popular non-*Bt* varieties should remain available to improve chances that some non-*Bt* rice fields (refuges) will exist. Sufficient seed supplies of non-*Bt* varieties should be maintained.
4. Implement a resistance monitoring program. Several methodologies can be used to monitor pest populations for the evolution of resistance to *Bt* cultivars (Andow and Hutchinson 1998). The use of "sentinel plots," in which insect damage is monitored in unsprayed fields of *Bt* cultivars, is perhaps the most practical for rice-growing areas. Resistance monitoring programs can serve as an early warning system for governments and farmers and provide valuable information for improved deployment of future pest-resistant cultivars.

More than 20 research groups in many countries have produced *Bt* rice. Most of the lines produced do not meet recommendation 1, and very few lines meet recommendation 2. Scientists and governments will soon be faced with decisions of whether to release single-toxin and/or low-dose *Bt* rice cultivars to farmers. Their decisions should be based on long-term as well as short-term benefits. Many farmers would benefit from growing *Bt* rice, but in most areas yield increases would be modest. Stem borers are usually low-level, chronic pests. Based on an extensive survey

of farmers' fields in Asia, stem borers were estimated to cause an overall mean yield loss of 2.4% (Savary et al 2000). In areas where stem borers are not an urgent problem, it would seem sensible to delay the release of *Bt* rice until a two-toxin, high-dose cultivar is available. In areas where stem borer damage is high, it must be realized that low-dose and/or single-toxin cultivars might not remain effective for very long.

There are currently no proven alternatives to *Bt* toxins for use in transgenic plants to control caterpillar pests. Clearly, *Bt* toxins are a valuable natural resource that must be used with great care.

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- ...that IRRI Library staff are waiting right now to receive your requests³?

We hope to be of service to you soon!

¹Maximum of 50 pages per request

²Web address: <http://ricelib.irri.cgiar.org>

³Write to Carmelita Austria at this address:
Library and Documentation Service,
International Rice Research Institute,
MCPO Box 3127, Makati City 1271, Philippines.
E-mail address: c.austria@cgiar.org